

Assessing Policy Influence on Demand-Responsive Transit Systems: A Framework for DRTS Implementation

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Abstract

Budget constraints related to the development of transportation infrastructure are one of the reasons for the underdevelopment of public transportation services in rural towns of Taiwan. Thus, it is a very difficult question for local governments to provide public transportation services with a high service level in rural areas. In order to improve public transportation services in rural towns, the directorate general of highways of the ministry of transportation and communications has promoted the DRTS service since 2016 and has been promoting DRTS services for towns that lack of public services in Taiwan. This study chose Pingtung County's DRTS route as the research target and used regression analysis to find out the key performance factors in the implementation of the DRTS service. The study found that the establishment a DRTS information platform, the route for purpose of school, the number of people under 18 years old, the number of people over 65 years old, the type of buses used, and the average mileage were the factors that influenced the departure frequency of the DRTS service. The research methodology, findings, and management implications of this study can provide a reference and easy-to-analyze for towns to promote and analyze the effectiveness of the routes and to improve the DRTS routes.

Keywords: DRTS, performance analysis, regression analysis

I. Introduction

Due to the diverse reasons, capabilities, and opportunities for people to travel, the diverse user needs of all travel groups in remote areas face multiple issues and challenges. Given the considerable inflexibility of traditional bus systems, residents with long-distance travel needs, low local population density, or even temporary needs (such as travelers) or seasonal factors rely heavily on private transport (Gronau, 2017; Mattioli, 2014). To address the transportation service problem in remote areas, the introduction of Demand Response Transportation Services (DRTS) can provide public sectors with a flexible public transport service, defining the routes and schedules of operating vehicles based on residents' needs. Mahour Rahimi (2020) proposed that the goal of DRTS services is to provide services when: (1) demand density is too low to support adequate and economical regular transport services, or (2) the individuals served have mobility restrictions or conditions that prevent them from reaching fixed-route bus stops (e.g., distance or lack of sufficient sidewalks). In this context, governments and relevant agencies, considering the varying needs and possibilities of different groups in remote areas, have proposed different DRTS (Dedicated Transportation Services) or encouraged carpooling. These solutions can improve transportation inconvenience in remote areas (Mounce et al., 2020; Alonso-González et al., 2018; Bauchinger et al., 2021; Wright, 2013). Furthermore, in areas with advanced information and communication technologies or densely populated urban areas, similar but more convenient solutions have emerged, such as car and motorcycle sharing (Cohen and Kietzmann, 2014; Ferrero et al., 2018; Jochem et al., 2020).

As a sustainable public transportation service alternative to private cars (Anburuvel et al., 2022), DRTS urgently needs to find and implement a sustainable public transportation operation model that

is environmentally friendly, socially inclusive, and economically viable under the current operating model. However, transportation decisions are usually made based on traditional economic methods, including monetary costs and efficiency (Marsden et al., 2010). However, as a public service industry, the transportation sector cannot judge effectiveness based on operating performance like private enterprises; the effectiveness of resource input and output should be the primary consideration. Public transportation in remote areas of Taiwan has always been a challenge for the government in transportation management. Distance factors and supply-demand imbalances have led operators to apply for route closures or non-renewal upon expiration, creating a vicious cycle in operation and management (Hu et al., 2013). To meet the transportation needs of remote areas, the central government can only provide services through local township offices. However, as a new type of transportation service, its implementation has also encountered challenges, with demand being raised but its effectiveness not being particularly prominent. To enable future adopters of the Happy Bus service to evaluate the best operational model and manage it effectively, this study first collected past literature on transportation measurement, identified key metrics, then collected data, and finally analyzed the data to identify the key factors influencing the operational model.

The chapters of this study are explained as follows: Previous related research is reviewed in Chapter 2, which also describes the progress made in Pingtung County. Chapter 3 defines the research question, relevant variables, and the selection of statistical methods, and the results are presented in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 gives the conclusions and future research directions.

II. Literature Review

2.1 Taiwan Happiness Bus Route Status and Pingtung Operational Results

The Happiness Bus Service is a demand-responsive transit service (DRTS) project launched by the Directorate General of Highways, Ministry of Transportation and Communications, throughout Taiwan in 2016. The aim of this service is to provide public transportation services to residents in remote areas through a sustainable operating model, with effective and diversified subsidies, and to improve the accessibility of public transportation to these areas. Current subsidies for the Happiness Bus Service must meet the following conditions (Source: Directorate General of Highways, Ministry of Transportation and Communications).

1. Remote subsidy routes that have been discontinued and have no operators to take over their services;
2. Discontinued subsidized routes in remote areas;
3. Local governments plan to develop new, remote routes, but businesses have no intention of operating them;
4. Demand-responsive transportation model for last-mile delivery in metropolitan areas;
5. Other items such as subsidized routes in remote areas or those with poor passenger carrying capacity, as determined by the competent authority.

This study first compiles information on the current implementation status of DRTS (Road Traffic Safety Administration) and related operational data in Taiwan. The first step is to review the DRTS routes within the region. As of October 8, 2021, the number of routes operated by public transport-style taxis in New Taipei City is 5, Hsinchu City 2, Miaoli County 1, Taichung City 15, Yunlin County 2, Tainan City 11, Kaohsiung City 55, Pingtung County 19, Taitung County 9, and Yilan County 1. Meanwhile, the number of routes operated by Happiness Bus in Taipei City is 2, New Taipei City 6, Taoyuan City 8, Hsinchu County 8, Miaoli County 31, Nantou County 16, Yunlin County 1, Chiayi County 13, Pingtung County 35, Yilan County 7, Hualien County 12, Taitung County 25, and Kinmen County 1. To address the last-mile transportation needs of people in remote areas, by the end of 2021,

321 "Happy Bus" routes had been implemented in 120 townships and districts nationwide. Among these counties and cities, Pingtung County had the most routes, totaling 35. Currently, in addition to serving nine indigenous townships, "Happy Bus" services are also being implemented in areas with insufficient transportation services (such as Fangshan Township). Therefore, this study uses Pingtung County as a case study to understand the implementation status of "Happy Bus" in various townships within Pingtung County.

Pingtung County is one of the counties actively promoting the "Happy Bus" program, and Chunri Township within the county was selected as a national model for promoting the Happy Bus in 2016. The purpose of planning and launching the Happy Bus program in Pingtung County is to provide access from remote areas to major hubs within Pingtung County (such as hospitals and stations), truly implementing the Directorate General of Highways' just policy of providing transportation to remote areas (as shown in Figure 1). Since the implementation of the Happiness Bus policy in Pingtung County, the number of passengers has increased year by year (Figure 2). Each township has also planned appropriate transportation systems to provide services according to the needs of different customer groups, making it more convenient for people to seek medical treatment, go to school, and shop.

Figure 1. Purpose of the Pingtung County Happiness Bus Service

2.2 Discussion on DRTS Operation Models at Home and Abroad

2.2.1 Types and Advantages/Disadvantages of DRTS Abroad

From past literature, many scholars have categorized different DRTS schemes and then analyzed and evaluated their feasibility. For classification, this study references the six variables proposed by Poltimäe et al. (2022). These six variables are analyzed based on commonly used public transport factors (1) routes, (2) stops, and (3) dispatchability, dividing existing foreign public transport services into fixed, semi-flexible, and flexible door-to-door services. Secondly, considering other non-economic factors such as (4) booking requirements, (5) whether vehicles are shared with other passengers, and (6) vehicle type, services can be categorized into designated sightseeing buses, semi-flexible DRT, flexible door-to-door DRT, ride-sharing, and shared transportation. These indicators are considered the most relevant by the authors. Finally, the characteristics of these DRTS services are described in Table 1.

Figure 1. Purpose of the Pingtung County Happiness Bus Service

Table 1 Types of DRTS abroad

type	route	Stops	Scheduling	Booking	Whether the means of transport are disclosed or not	Vehicle type
Regular buses	Fixed	Fixed, can be skipped	Fixed	unnecessary	shared	Buses, minibuses
Designated sightseeing bus	Fixed	Fixed	Fixed	Required	shared	bus
Semi-elastic DRT	Fixed, semi-flexible*	semi-elastic**	Fixed, flexible	Required	shared	Bus, minibus, car
Flexible door-to-door DRT	Flexible	Flexible	Flexible	Required	Shared, Private	minibus, car
carpooling	Flexible	semi-elastic****	Flexible	Required	private	car
Shared transportation	semi-elastic	semi-elastic****	semi-elastic	Required	shared	car

* Routes with predefined stops can be skipped and services can be provided in a flexible order based on current demand.

** Stops can be predefined along routes or within areas, and services can be skipped and provided in a flexible order based on current needs.**

*** Services operating on fixed and demand-based schedules, based on a daily or weekly basis.

**** Depends on pick-up and drop-off locations

Traditional bus services have fixed routes, schedules, and stops, and do not require reservations; passengers can board as long as they arrive at the stop within a set time. However, this characteristic results in poor route or scheduling flexibility, excessively long distances between stops, and inconvenience for those with poor health or the elderly. DRT services can better meet the needs of local residents, but more flexible services may also increase operating costs. Therefore, choosing a

suitable operating model is an important consideration for operators implementing such services in the future. Table 2 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of various public transportation service types in this study.

Table 2 Advantages and disadvantages of traditional bus services and different DRTS (Digital Routes and Transportation Systems)

	Advantage	Shortcoming
Regular buses	+ Fixed stops and routes are easy to understand	- Inflexible routes, stops, or scheduling - Low departure frequency - Long travel time - Stops not convenient for all users - Inconvenient for people with poor health (requiring physical labor) - Scheduling cannot consider all user groups and purposes (commuting, healthcare, grocery shopping, etc.)
Designated sightseeing bus	+ Short travel time + Fixed stops and routes are easy to understand	- Local residents cannot use it
Semi-elastic DRT	+ Shorter travel time + Additional connections to stops or areas based on local residents' needs + Flexibility depends on the specific DRT solution and can be provided at different levels + Relatively low cost	-Availability depends on the designated service area -Smaller vehicles may not be able to meet the demand.
Door-to-door DRT	+ As frequent as possible + Short trip time + Waiting time at the starting point + Very flexible + More popular with groups who prefer solo travel	Depending on vehicle availability , it could become more expensive.
carpooling	Frequent departures as much as possible + ability to plan your own trips + short trip times + high privacy + very flexible + not very high	- Depends on car availability (which is often a challenge) - Parking issues may arise at the destination.
Shared transportation	+ Short travel time + High flexibility if supply and demand are balanced (which is usually a challenge) + Typically, the cost is not very high	- Availability depends on the traveler's route - Safety concerns regarding unknown drivers

2.2.2 Summary of Domestic DRTS Operation Models, Types, and Applicable Conditions

The current DRTS (Diverterless Transportation System) operation models in Taiwan are divided into two types: public bus-style taxis and "Happiness Bus" (Happiness Bus 2.0). However, further

research revealed that other ministries (such as the Ministry of Health and Welfare and the Ministry of Education) have also invested in similar transportation services. Therefore, this study expands the scope of ministries to identify services similar to DRTS, including rehabilitation buses, long-term care shuttles, day care shuttles, education priority zones, and transportation for caregivers. This study focuses on rehabilitation buses, long-term care shuttles, day care shuttles, education priority zones, and transportation for caregivers. Services such as public bus-style taxis and "Happiness Bus" (Happiness Bus 2.0) have been described in detail in previous literature. This study focuses on other services with similar operating models mentioned in the literature.

1. Long-term care shuttle/day care center

To assist elderly individuals with moderate to severe disabilities by providing transportation to and from long-term care and related services, and to address their difficulties in using general public transportation, thus protecting their right to mobility. The service is available to individuals at Long-Term Care Needs Level (CMS) 4 or above, and is limited to use for round-trip transportation between home and medical facilities for medical treatment or rehabilitation (including dialysis) within the care plan, and must meet one of the following conditions:

- a. Seniors aged 65 and above; b. Indigenous people aged 55-64; c. People with disabilities; d. People with dementia aged 50 and above. The charging methods are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Long-term care connection fee structure

User identity	Within the monthly payment limit	Exceeding the monthly payment limit
Long-term care for low-income households	0	Table amount × 1/2
Long-term care for low-income households	[Table Amount × 10%] × 1/2	
Long-term care general households	[Amount × 30%] × 1/2	

2. Education Priority Area

To achieve balanced urban and rural education development, narrow regional education gaps, and promote education priority areas to reduce the urban-rural education gap, thereby realizing the ideals of "equal educational opportunities" and "social fairness and justice," the target audience is:

- Students in rural towns that do not have elementary or junior high schools, and whose schools are located in areas with inconvenient transportation.
- Students in remote mountainous areas face difficulties accessing education due to changes in their geographical environment and the continued operation of public transportation.
- Schools on outlying islands or in remote areas with inconvenient transportation

The current model mainly adopts the principle of temporary car rental. If a car cannot be rented, one must apply to purchase a shuttle vehicle or receive a subsidy for transportation expenses.

3. Caregiver Transportation

Currently, most of Taiwan's indigenous peoples reside in the mountainous areas of eastern

Taiwan. Due to slower resource development and less convenient and rapid transportation infrastructure compared to the west, and because the elderly often live in more remote and scattered locations, their willingness to go out is reduced, and local health and wellness centers face numerous challenges in providing transportation services. Therefore, this service, in addition to handling the caregivers' own commutes and official duties, also provides transportation for elderly people in various areas. This typically involves transportation between the elderly person's home and the health and wellness center, as well as transportation when medical care is needed.

4. Rehabilitation Bus

Currently, rehabilitation buses in Taiwan are operated independently by each county and city government. Some counties and cities lease vehicles for operation. Service recipients must be persons with disabilities registered in the local county (city) and holding a disability certificate. Fees vary according to the regulations of each county (city), with different service contents and pricing standards. Users usually need to make reservations and confirm in advance by phone. To uphold the principles of fairness, impartiality, and transparency in accepting public reservations, the service provides door-to-door transportation and categorizes service recipients according to their disability level into Special A, A, and B (Table 4).

Table 4 Service Recipient Category Levels (Based on Disability Manual)

Disability level	Disability categories
Special Grade A	vegetative state People with severe upper and lower limb disabilities who require crutches or wheelchairs
Grade A	Severe organ damage Severe or severe limb disabilities other than Grade A People with severe or severe visual impairment People with multiple disabilities (including limb disabilities)
Grade B	Other categories (non-A grade)

Based on the above descriptions of DRTS service models in the region, the relevant content of this study is summarized in Table 5 below.

Table 5 Domestic DRTS Operation Model

Category	Funding sources	License Category	Driving qualifications	Service recipients
yellow bus	Highway Administration	Commercial passenger vehicles	Professional camp registration	All are available for boarding.
Happiness Bus	Highway Administration	Operating large/small passenger vehicles	Professional camp registration	All are available for boarding.
Happiness Bus 2.0	Highway Administration, etc.	Operating large/small passenger vehicles	Professional camp registration	All are available for boarding.
Rehabilitation Bus	Ministry of Health and Welfare	Private/Rental Passenger Car	Professional camp registration	disability certificate
Long-term care	Ministry of	Private/Rental	Professional	Long-term care

Category	Funding sources	License Category	Driving qualifications	Service recipients
connection	Health and Welfare	Passenger Car	camp registration	eligibility
Rizhao shuttle	Ministry of Health and Welfare	Private/Rental Passenger Car	Campaign in progress	Long-term care eligibility
Education priority area	Ministry of Education	Commercial buses	Professional camp registration	Children below high school level
Traffic service personnel	Indigenous Peoples Council	-	-	Indigenous people, caregivers

2.3 Selection of Performance Measurement Factors

A review of relevant domestic and international research reveals that public transportation performance evaluation indicators are generally categorized into two main types: "operational performance indicators" and "service performance indicators." Regarding operational performance in the transportation industry, most domestic scholars agree with Fielding's (1987) performance evaluation framework. His performance evaluation indicators are based on the efficiency of resource utilization and output utilization rate between transportation inputs and outputs, while also examining the costs required to provide transportation services and the degree of utilization of those services. Therefore, in recent years, the selection of performance indicators for the transportation industry has largely referenced Fielding's Performance Classification Scheme for public transportation systems. The basis for selecting performance evaluation indicators is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Performance classification diagram proposed by Fielding

The architecture divides the operational activities of the transportation industry into three dimensions: service inputs, service outputs, and service consumption. It then uses the relationship between any two of these dimensions to form three performance indicators for measuring the operational performance of the transportation industry: (1) "Cost efficiency" explores the relationship between the resource inputs and outputs of public transportation operators to reflect the economic efficiency, technical efficiency, and internal management efficiency of operators; (2) "Service effectiveness" explores the relationship between the service outputs provided by operators and user consumption to measure the utilization of the services provided by operators; and (3) "Cost effectiveness" explores the relationship between the resource inputs of operators and user consumption, which can be obtained by multiplying the cost efficiency indicator and the service effectiveness indicator, thus providing a comprehensive measure of cost efficiency and service effectiveness.

Since public transportation services are a basic necessity for the public, the evaluation of public transportation performance focuses not only on operational performance but also on service performance. Currently in Taiwan's urban passenger transport sector, transportation bureaus of various county and city governments have incorporated factors such as untidy staff attire, unclean bus interiors, buses failing to stop at designated stops, and poor staff service attitudes into their bus service quality assessment models. However, the social, environmental, and health issues related to transportation services have not received sufficient attention. Only in recent years have social and environmental factors been incorporated into transportation-related decision-making (Holden et al., 2019; Karjalainen and Juhola, 2021), leading to the development of relevant indicators. This study compiles domestic and international literature, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Explanation of Domestic and International Literature Indicators

Author	Indicators used in the article
Hu Kaijie, Feng Zhengmin, and Wang Junwei (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Distance to remote areas: ● Proportion of driving in remote areas ● average population density ● Average income level ● Route-weighted population density ● Route weighted level
Zhang Chaoneng and Wu Zhaoyi (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coverage of public transport space services in rural areas ● Guest occupancy rate
Shioda et al. (2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Idle time ● Delay time ● travel time ● Average travel distance
Anderson and Khan (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● productivity: ● Operating cost per hour of vehicle operation ● Operating cost per mile driven by the vehicle ● Operating cost per passenger trip ● Average passenger journey length ● Average travel time ● Hourly utilization ● Mileage utilization ● Operating cost adoption rate
Baratian-Ghorghi and Ahmadianyazdi (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bus accident rate ● Potential hidden accidents caused by bus drivers ● Potential hidden accidents in passenger transport companies ● Accidents related to maintenance ● Bus driver's lost workdays due to injury ● Crimes on buses ● Safety standards provided by the passenger transport company ● Customers' views on the safety and security systems of the transportation system

Author	Indicators used in the article
Lakatos et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Population density ● Traffic surveys ● Travel distance ● Operating costs
Kaufman et al. (2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Travel time ● Travel length ● population density
Poltimäe et al. (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of retirees ● Working-age population ● Families with children

III. Research Methods

The implementation of Demand Response Transportation Services (DRTS) can provide public sectors with a flexible public transportation service; however, more flexible services may also increase operating costs. As a means to meet the basic transportation needs of people in remote areas, the evaluation of public transportation performance should not only focus on operational performance but also incorporate social, environmental, and health issues into transportation-related decision-making. Understanding which factors influence the operation of DRTS will allow future operators to choose appropriate operating models that meet the needs of residents in remote areas while avoiding increased operating costs for the operators.

3.1 Model Establishment

Based on a review of relevant literature, the indicators for evaluating the operational performance of public transportation are mostly analyzed using variables such as population/density, route distance, passenger volume, number of trips, mileage, and operating costs/subsidies. However, the main purpose of the demonstration cases of public transportation in rural areas of Taiwan is to improve the accessibility of public transportation services in these areas. Therefore, this study collects relevant DRTS operational evaluation indicators and incorporates variables related to route time and spatial coverage to explore the current status of public transportation operations and examine whether Taiwan's public transportation can provide the most basic services. The regression model established in this study uses the number of trips as the variable, which is a count variable; the independent variables include community population, service type (including fixed/reservation), reservation method (whether there is an information platform), travel purpose (medical/education/other livelihood purposes), number of people under 18 years old, number of people over 65 years old, necessity of transfer (whether it is direct), the mode of transport used (taxi) (4 people), mode of transport (minibus) (7-8 people), mode of transport (medium bus) (20-21 people), and average operating mileage (km). In this model, only the community population, the number of people under 18 years old, the number of people over 65 years old, and the average operating mileage are used as continuous variables. The remaining independent variables are used as categorical variables, depending on the specific circumstances of each route. The regression model is shown in Equation 1:

$$Y_{Actual\ number\ of\ shifts} = f(Socio\ economic\ characteristics, route\ characteristics) \quad (1)$$

3.2 Operational Definition

3.2.1 Definitions of Independent Variable and Strain Number

This section explains how to measure the research variables and how to calculate them. For the strain variables, this study uses the actual number of shifts occurring annually as the model. The independent variables are explained in Table 7.

Table 7 Definition of Operant Types of Independent Variables

Category Description	Operational definition
Community population	Based on the national statistics of the Republic of China in that year
Service type (fixed)	The announcements have a fixed schedule on the county government website.
Service type (appointment)	There is no fixed schedule; reservations are made by phone or other information systems.
Reservation methods (with or without an information platform)	Provides QR code, cord, and other related information.
Secondary purpose of the trip (medical treatment)	The route passes by medical institutions.
Secondary purpose of travel (studying)	The route passes by educational institutions such as junior high schools and elementary schools.
Secondary travel purpose (other livelihood issues)	The route passes through other non-medical and non-educational stations.
Population under 18 years old	Based on the population statistics under the age of 18 in the National Statistics Bulletin of the Republic of China that year
Population aged 65 and over	Based on the population statistics of the Republic of China over the age of 65 in that year's National Statistics Bulletin
Necessity of transfer (whether it's a direct route)	The route requires other public transportation to reach.
Transportation vehicle (small yellow)	The route is served by passenger vehicles with 5 seats or less.
Transportation (minibus)	The route is served by 7–8-seater buses.
Transportation vehicle (minibus)	The route is served by 20–21-seater buses.
Average annual operating mileage (km)	Total annual mileage divided by the number of trips per year

3.2.2 Setting Category Variables

In observing categorical variables, this study considers situations where independent variables are non-quantifiable, making it difficult to measure them effectively, such as the provision of yellow bus transportation. Therefore, this study includes such cases in the discussion to further understand the

impact of these variables on the regression model. The categorical variable settings are explained in Table 8.

Table 8. Instructions for setting category variables

Category Description	Operational definition	Consideration methods	Code name setting
Service type (fixed)	The announcements have a fixed schedule on the county government website.	fixed	1
		No	0
Service type (appointment)	There is no fixed schedule; reservations are made by phone or other information systems.	have	1
		No	0
Information Platform	Are there any information platforms where I can make reservations?	have	1
		No	0
Secondary purpose of the trip (medical treatment)	The route passes by medical institutions.	have	1
		No	0
Secondary purpose of travel (studying)	The route passes by educational institutions such as junior high schools and elementary schools.	have	1
		No	0
Travel destination (people's livelihood)	The route passes through other non-medical and non-educational stations.	have	1
		No	0
Necessity of transfer	The route requires other public transportation to reach.	have	1
		No	0
Xiao Huang	The route is served by passenger vehicles with 5 seats or less.	have	1
		No	0
minibus	The route is served by 7-8 seater buses.	have	1
		No	0
China-Pakistan	The route is served by 20-21 seater buses.	have	1
		No	0

IV. Research Results

This study collected route data for all Happiness Bus routes in Pingtung County from 2016 to 2021. However, the Happiness Bus operation model is a continuously updated model, and some early data may be missing due to insufficient data. Therefore, this study removed data from months with missing data and initially collected 204 route records, which were used as the basis for the research and discussion.

4.1 Narrative Statistics

4.1.1 Time distribution of passengers

This study first analyzes the number of passengers in Pingtung County each month, and finds that the number of passengers in February, July, and August is lower than in other months (as shown in Figure 4). Therefore, this study first considers the purpose of the Pingtung County Happiness Bus service, and it can be inferred that the reduced number of passengers is due to the fact that these three months are during the school winter and summer vacations, and there are no school buses running. This results in a lower number of passengers in these three months compared to other months, which is consistent with the reality that all townships stop operating school buses in March.

Figure 4. Monthly ride statistics for Pingtung County

4.1.2 Types of Transportation Utilities Selected in Townships and Villages of Pingtung County

In the past, the promotion of the Happy Bus service primarily relied on medium-sized buses, which influenced the choice of transportation in various townships of Pingtung County. Figure 5 shows that in each township, routes using 20 or 21-seat medium-sized buses were more numerous than those using 7-8 seat minibuses or yellow buses. However, in recent years, due to the Directorate General of Highways actively inviting taxi operators to join the Happy Bus service, and because roads in remote areas or indigenous townships are too narrow for medium-sized buses to effectively access communities, routes using minibuses and taxis have gradually increased.

4.1.3 Bus departure schedules for each township

As explained in Section 2.1, Pingtung County has the most routes for the "Happy Bus" service, with all its indigenous townships having implemented it. Table 9 summarizes the usage of the Happy Bus in Pingtung County's townships over the past four years (2018-2021). The table shows a gradual increase in the number of Happy Bus riders in Pingtung County's indigenous townships, indicating a growing acceptance of the service. Pingtung County's experience can serve as a reference for other townships willing to implement the service.

Figure 5. Types of vehicles selected for the route

Table 9 Annual Passenger Circulation in Townships of Pingtung County

	Subtotal of 2018	Subtotal for 2019	Subtotal for 2020	2021 subtotal
Sandimen Township	14194	20232	23452	14707
Peony Township	486	712	1049	1250
Laiyi Township	-	952	3047	4319
Fangshan Township	-	-	-	255
Kasuga Village	29736	31386	28085	23906
Taiwu Township	468	1732	851	1124
Lion Township	2423	2596	2771	1723
Manzhou Township	-	-	187	12776
Majia Township	31	7842	10224	7984

- Indicates that the Happiness Bus service has not yet been launched.

4.2 Use of Regression Analysis

The Happy Bus operating model is a continuously updated model. Early data may have been incomplete due to insufficient data. Additionally, when collecting the independent variable "whether there is a transfer," this variable was excluded from the model's measurement to ensure stability, as current routes all use door-to-door service. Finally, 165 data points were used for regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis was employed for comparison, and stepwise regression analysis was used to eliminate variables with excessive multicollinearity and those without significant impact. The final independent variables selected for the model are: whether an information platform is established, purpose of education, number of people under 18 years old, number of people over 65 years old, type of minibus used, and average mileage (as shown in Table 10).

The following section explains the relationship between the establishment of the information platform, the purpose of education, users under 18 years old, users over 65 years old, the type of minibus used, the average mileage, and the actual number of trips, established using multiple linear regression. The actual number of trips is the strain variable. Except for the number of people under 18 years old and the number of people over 65 years old, which are continuous variables, the rest are categorical variables. The results of the analysis using the multiple linear regression model are shown in Table 11.

Table 10 Basic Statistical Analysis of the Model

	Average	Standard deviation	Number
Train schedule	153.3879	281.1714	165
Whether or not an information platform is established	0.2182	0.41427	165
Secondary purpose of travel (studying)	0.4606	0.49996	165
Population under 18 years old	931.3455	207.6708	165
Population aged 65 and over	711.1818	213.2333	165
Using minibus transport	0.5758	0.49573	165

Average mileage	27.9259	21.73787	165
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Table 11 Regression Analysis Results

model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient	t	Significance
	The estimated value of B	Standard error	Beta Distribution		
(constant)	121.971	109.625		1.113	0.268
Whether or not an information platform is established	157.812	57.815	0.233	2.73	0.007
Secondary purpose of travel (studying)	137.068	44.877	0.244	3.054	0.003
Population under 18 years old	-0.339	0.1	-0.251	-3.401	0.001
Population aged 65 and over	0.375	0.098	0.285	3.826	0.000
Using minibus transport	101.539	43.133	0.179	2.354	0.020
Average mileage	-2.705	0.996	-0.209	-2.714	0.007
Adj R ² =0.224, MSE= 545595.939, RMSE= 61340.693					

The final regression model of the operating performance of the Happiness Bus constructed in this study is shown in Equation 2.

$$T\text{- class trips} = 0.233X \text{ Whether or not an information platform is established} + 0.244X \text{ Purpose of trip (study)} - 0.251X \text{ Number of people under 18 years old} + 0.285X \text{ Number of people over 65 years old} + 0.179X \text{ Type of minibus used} - 0.209X \text{ Average mileage} + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

The regression results show that if an information platform is available for public reservations, each reservation will result in an additional number of trips. Similarly, if the purpose of the trip is school, or if an additional senior citizen aged 65 or older is traveling on a minibus (a vehicle with 20-21 seats), the number of trips will increase. However, the number of people under 18 and an additional kilometer of average mileage will decrease the number of trips.

4.3 Management Implications of the Model

Based on domestic and international research and a practical understanding of the actual operation of the Happiness Bus service within Pingtung County, this study measures the actual number of departures based on factors such as community population, service type (including fixed/reservation), reservation method (existence of information platform), travel purpose (medical/education/other livelihood purposes), number of residents under 18 years old, number of residents over 65 years old, necessity of transfer (whether it is a direct route), mode of transport used (taxi/minibus/medium bus), and average operating mileage (km). The center uses current operational data from Pingtung County as a sample to investigate the factors influencing the frequency of departures.

The study results show that the community population and whether or not there are fixed routes do not affect the actual number of departures. Regarding the purpose of travel, medical treatment or

other livelihood-related purposes (such as shopping) have no impact on the actual number of departures. This is because the purpose of travel is clear and has a fixed itinerary; if the purpose of passengers' travel can be understood, the empty bus rate can be reduced. Furthermore, using taxis with 5 or fewer seats and minibuses with 7-8 seats does not affect the actual number of departures. This is because the current township offices can monitor passenger numbers and provide corresponding resources, avoiding excessive resource allocation.

While fixed routes and schedules don't affect the actual number of departures, providing convenient booking methods can indeed increase the frequency of services. Furthermore, the number of people under 18 and over 65 influences the number of departures. Further investigation revealed that towns with fewer people under 18 maintain a certain number of departures, but those with students traveling to school increase the frequency. Therefore, for school-related trips, the Happiness Bus service must better align with the actual needs of educational institutions in the town and allocate public transportation resources appropriately. Additionally, an increase in average operating mileage (km) indicates a more circuitous route and longer travel time. Ultimately, people will likely choose to use private transportation to reach their destinations, which does not benefit the promotion of the Happiness Bus service.

V. Conclusions and Recommendations

In the past, public transportation in remote areas of Taiwan has always been a challenge for the government in managing transportation. Distance factors and supply-demand imbalances have led traditional bus operators to apply for route closures or non-renewal upon expiration, creating a vicious cycle for transportation services in remote areas. By the end of 2021, the Directorate General of Highways of the Ministry of Transportation and Communications had implemented 321 "Happy Bus" routes in 120 townships and districts nationwide. The "Happy Bus" service provides a flexible public transportation service to remote areas, allowing local residents to reach important transportation hubs at reasonable prices without relying on private vehicles. However, more flexible services may also increase operating costs, deterring potential operators. Therefore, in addition to operational and service performance indicators, social and health-related performance indicators must be incorporated to develop an operational model that balances transportation demand and business operations.

This study first collected indicators used in recent years to measure the operational, service, and social health aspects of transportation. Raw data was then collected using the Pingtung County's "Happy Bus" program. Finally, the data was processed and regression analysis was used to identify key factors influencing the operational model. The study found that, based on Pingtung County's current implementation, factors such as the design of the information platform for public reservations, travel purpose, passenger type (e.g., students under 18 or seniors over 65), route mileage, and mode of transport selection affect the frequency of Happy Bus departures. Data from the Pingtung County Government's Happy Bus service shows that ridership has increased year by year, indicating public acceptance of the service. Currently, township offices are able to grasp passenger demand and ridership, providing corresponding resources to avoid excessive investment and control costs.

When promoting the Happy Bus service, the transportation departments of each county and municipal government should first identify the target audience for the route and communicate with stakeholders in the area. Those in need prioritize accessibility, convenience, and fairness, while the promoting transportation departments and local regulatory bodies focus on urban-rural development, law enforcement, and the fairness of funding allocation. Central regulatory bodies, on the other hand, emphasize the enforcement of regulations. Given the different considerations of various stakeholders, this model analysis can serve as a topic for discussion in townships and among stakeholders who wish to promote the Happy Bus operation model.

Finally, this study aims to establish a robust and measurable regression model for evaluating the

operational performance of the Happy Bus service, using operational data from the Pingtung County Government as a data source for model calibration. Future research will continue to collect Happy Bus data from other regions of Taiwan to examine whether the model can measure the operational effectiveness of Happy Bus services in other towns and villages across the island.

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